

Research Article

Rural Households' Perception of the Expanded Programme on Children Immunization (Epi) in the Southwest of Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out in the South West of Nigeria. Three states out of six were selected namely; Ekiti, Ondo and Osun States. Three Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each State while two communities were sampled from each LGA. In all, 18 communities were used for the study. From each community, ten households were randomly interviewed giving a total of 180 households. Data collected were analyzed using frequency tables and percentages and also Chi-square analysis. The study found that only 18 percent of the respondents did not participate in Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) while 56 percent had high participation. Further finding showed that the respondents had favorable attitude towards EPI, and as well, perceived it as important. Furthermore, it was found that age, marital status, household size and religion had significant relationship with the respondents' perception towards EPI. It was recommended that the zero payment status for the programme should be continued and the services of town criers in the communities should be encouraged as rural people placed much premium on information disseminated from town criers as a form of reminder.

Key Words: Children, Households, Immunization, Perception, Rural.

INTRODUCTION

The year 2008 was the year recorded for a general outcry for global food shortage. In Nigeria, food prices went up between 75 and 100 percent increases. The various levels of government had to intervene through the release of the reserved food, particularly, the grains to the populace. Nigeria's food crisis may be attributed to the long time neglect of agriculture by the successive government administrations since the advent of petroleum in Nigerian market (Ayoola, 2001). While food production increases at 2.2 percent annually, the population increases at 3.2 percent annually (FAO, 2002).

Many other reasons have been adduced for the relegation of agriculture by many researchers. One of these is the migration of the youth and able bodied men and women to the urban areas. This results in the abandonment of farming enterprise into the hands of the aged people who still maintain subsistence practice of farming (Alfred, 2004). It was believed that if the children and the youth were encouraged to live in the rural area and contribute to food production, the effect of food crisis could be ameliorated (Adedoyin, 2005).

However, apart from the lack of social facilities that could encourage the children and the youth to remain in the rural areas, is the issue of ill-health and diseases. The causes of ill-health and diseases may be attributed to hereditary or nutritional factors. According to one source, it has been estimated that 100,000 children are being born each year with irreversible brain damage because their mothers lacked iodine prior to and during pregnancy (ICCIDD, 2002). Vitamins A deficiency (VAD) has been regarded as still the leading cause of preventable blindness in children. For instance, optimal vitamin A status is necessary for the immune system to function normally; subclinical deficiency has equally been linked to increased childhood illness and death. It is estimated that improving

the vitamin A status of children would decrease overall child mortality rates by 25 percent, measles death rates by 50 percent and death caused by diarrhea by 40 percent (UNICEF, 2002).

To reduce the level of incapacitation of the children and the youth by diseases, the Federal Government of Nigeria introduced the programme on immunization for the children, known as Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI). The programme has been intended to curb the effects of whooping cough (pertusis), tuberculosis, tetanus, poliomyelitis, measles and diphtheria. In the process, vaccines against the afore mentioned diseases, including Vitamin A and that of yellow fever prevention were being administered. The programme is held simultaneously throughout the whole federation bi-monthly. The exercise takes the practitioners from one household to another including schools, market places, religious houses and hospitals. It is assumed that if this programme is well embraced by the rural households, the killer diseases would be "kicked out" of the country. Hence, labor supply to farming would be enhanced. However, the use of herbal drugs, religious activities and fatalistic belief are still very much in practice among the rural households in Nigeria. (Ekong, 2003).

These beliefs, to a large extent serve as an alternative to the orthodox medical practice. It is therefore hypothesized that, households may have different perceptions towards the acceptance of EPI. It is on this basis that the study was undertaken to investigate the perception of the households towards the acceptance of EPI in the Southwest of Nigeria.

The main objective of the study therefore, was to investigate the households' perception towards the acceptance of Expanded Programme on Immunization in the Southwest of Nigeria. Specifically, the study;

- ascertained the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents
- assessed the level of participation in EPI by the respondents
- determined the perception of respondents towards the acceptance of EPI
- determined effects of respondents' socio-economic characteristics on their perception

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in the Southwest of Nigeria. A multi-stage random sampling technique was used. Three of six states that make up the zone were selected namely; Ekiti, Ondo and Osun States. In each State, three Local Government Areas were selected, giving a total of nine LGAs for the study. Two communities were sampled from each LGA while, ten households were randomly interviewed giving a total respondents of 180.

Data were collected by means of an interview schedule earlier pretested using odd and even numbered-item-correlation method ($r = .63$). Data analysis was done using frequencies, means, tables and percentages. Also used was Chi-square analysis.

Description of Variables

Socio-economic characteristics: These made up of the respondents' age, sex, and marital status, level of education, household size and occupation.

Level of participation: Respondents' assessment in percentage of the number of times EPI was carried out in the last two years. It was assumed that the exercise was carried out 12 times (since it is bi-monthly). Participants that scored not more than six times have low participation, while scores above six categorize the participants into high participation. It was assumed that scoring below the average of the number of the exercise (EPI) is low while above the average is taken as high.

Perception: Respondents were made to respond to some statements. The responses were measured on five-point Likert-scale of "strongly agree", "agree", "undecided", "disagree" and "strongly disagree". While some other statements were measured on four-point Likert-scale of very important, important, somewhat important, not important.

The scores for 5-point Likert-scale were 5,4,3,2 and 1 and for 4-point Likert-scale, it was 4, 3, 2, and 1. These scores were however, reversed for negative statements. Means score of less than 2.50, or between 2.50 and 3.50 and that above 3.50 were regarded as "Disagreed", "Indifferent" and "Agreed" respectively. Respectively too, the mean scores were taken as "not important", "important" and "very important".

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents (n = 180)

Socio-Economic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex:		
Male	13	7.0
Female	167	93.0
Age:		
< 25 years	59	31.0
26 – 35 years	79	44.0
36 – 45 years	25	14.0
46 – 55 years	13	7.0
> 56 years	4	2.0
Marital Status:		
Married	171	95.0
Widowed	9	5.0
Household Size:		
< 5	104	58.0
6 – 10	56	31.0
> 10	20	11.0
Level of Education:		
No formal education	22	12.0
Adult Education	14	8.0
Primary school education	99	55.0
Secondary school education	43	24.0
Tertiary education	2	1.0
Religion:		
Christianity	160	88.0
Islam	15	9.0
Traditional Religion	5	3.0
Occupation:		
Farming	49	27.0
Business	127	71.0
Public service	4	2.0

Table 1 show that 93 percent of the respondents were females while their ages ranged from youth to middle ages. It was also found that 95 percent were married while 5 percent were widowed. These results might be because much of the focus of the study was on the child-bearing households. High literacy of the respondents was also found. High literacy level could be a factor in the determination of the level of participation of the respondents in the EPI. The respondents also held one belief or the other which may also be a factor for the choice of what health practice they should adopt or not. Past studies (Jibowo, 1992, Alfred, 2006), agreed to the fact that person's belief has influence on the choice he/she makes. Further finding indicated that a larger percentage (98%) were self employed, implying their timely availability for the programme.

Table 2: Level of participation in EPI by the Respondents

Level of Participation	Frequency	Percentage
High participation	101	56.0
Low participation	47	26.0
Non participation	32	18.0
TOTAL	180	100.0

Findings as shown in Table 2, show that 56 percent of the respondents had high participation in EPI, 26 percent had low participation while 18 percent did not participate. By this result, it could be inferred that the households in the study area actually embraced the programme. This might however, be unconnected with the indoor to indoor

approach with which the programme was being executed. With the success of the programme, there is the prospect that there would be less deformed children in the near future which would likely ensure future human labor supplies.

Table 3: The Perception of Respondents Towards the Acceptance of EPI

ITEMS	SA(5)	A(4)	U(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	x
I am very much aware of EPI	540	207	27	18	4	4.4
I wholly agree with EPI as practiced	270	266	81	49	18	3.8
EPI prevents some debilitating						
Childhood diseases	252	144	11	29	13	2.5
There would have been less of the						
Handi-capped people if EPI has						
Long been in practice	475	132	27	36	21	3.9
EPI or not, it is God who protects	396	238	54	36	14	4.1
EPI cannot prevent what has been						
Destined to happen	30	101	32	130	90	2.1
I accept EPI just because it is free	135	86	43	144	45	2.5
I cannot spend my time on such exercise	9	54	54	180	405	3.9
EPI is a good policy of the government	522	230	27	7	5	4.4
I suggest we go back to our old practice	5	6	11	130	657	4.4
		VI(4)	I(3)	SI(2)	NI(1)	
Protecting the children from deadly						
Diseases		468	178	7	0	3.6
We need to prepare the children						
For healthy lives		504	135	11	2	3.6
Both the government and the parents						
Must cooperate		590	69	47	5	4.0
Children are sought out for everywhere						
For EPI		367	119	61	180	3.1
Defaulting parents should be sanctioned		353	189	22	18	3.2
Parents could be made to pay a token to EPI		230	151	97	23	2.8

Grand Mean = 4.41 and 3.38 respectively.

KEY:

SA (strongly Agree), A (Agree), U (Undecided), D (Disagree), SD (Strongly Disagree)
 VI (Very Important), I (Important), SI (Somewhat Important), NI (Not Important)

Result in Table 3 shows the Perception of respondents towards acceptance of EPI. There was an indication that the respondents were aware of EPI and agreed with its practices, however, the concept and prospects might not have been understood. This was because, while the respondents agreed (4.4, 3.8) on the awareness of the subject, they were in different (3.2) to the questions bothering on its essence.

Further result revealed that, the cooperation and participation of respondents could likely be secured as their perception towards the benefits of EPI found them to be important. They did not however, perceive that the defiants of the programme should be sanctioned. This may be due to the fact that, rural people would always want to defend themselves from anything that can cause pain due to the family values and solidarity inherent among them, Ekong (2003) agrees.

The summary of this finding is that, the respondents had positive perception (Grand mean of 4.41) towards acceptance of EPI but were indifferent (Grand mean of 3.38) towards its importance.

Table 4: Respondents' Perception of Source of Information on EPI

Information Source	Frequency	Percentage
Source:		
Television/Radio	146	81.0
Newspaper	5	3.0
Health Extension Officer	27	15.0
Friends/Relations	2	1.0
Perception on Source:		
Effective	129	72.0
Not effective	49	27.0
Don't know	2	1.0
Timeliness of information:		
Very timely	132	73.0
Timely	40	23.0
Not timely	7	4.0

Judging from the result on Table 4, respondents were found to have regarded the EPI program as being effective (72%) and Timely (96%). In addition, information on EPI was obtained by the respondents through the electronic media (81%), Newspaper (35), Health Extension Officers (15%) and Friends/relations (1%). Effectiveness and timeliness of information source have been found (Williams et al, 1984, Alfred et al, 2004) to play significant roles in the rate and level of adoption of technologies. This might be the reason while high participation in EPI (Table 2) was recorded among the respondents for this study. So also, electronic media appears to be the most accessible to the people and of course it also has the widest coverage.

Table 5: Immunization Pattern among the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Proportion of children immunized:		
All children	116	64.0
Not all the children	64	36.0
Age at which children were immunized:		
6 months	54	30.0
9 months	126	70.0
Mode of Immunization:		
At Health centers	104	57.7
At Home	76	42.3

Even when the information sources are effective and timely as in Table 4, not all the children could be immunized. For some, the children might have out grown the age of immunization before the awareness of the programme and for some they could still be skeptical of the programme when their children were growing up. In Table 5, only 64 percent had all their children immunized. This category might be those who were within the youth stage and who started their family lives within the period of the programme execution.

The result further indicated that 57.7% percent visited the health centre for the purpose of immunization while the health officers visited 42.3 percent at home. This result corroborates the earlier assertion that the door to door approach employed for the programme guarantees wider coverage. For instance, if it were made compulsory for the immunization to take place only at the health centers, probably 42.3 percent might not have been reached.

Table 6 shows the relationship between the respondent's socio-economic characteristics and their perception of EPI. It was found that age, marital status, household size and religion of the respondents had significant relationship with their perception of EPI. The implication of the result could be that, younger married respondents with younger children were more likely to have been involved in EPI than the required ages for EPI. Further implication of the significant state of relationship between respondent's household size, religion and their perception of EPI could be that both household size and religion have influence in the decision a household makes towards its welfare and health.

Table 6: Chi-Square Analysis of the Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents and their Perception of Expanded Programme on Immunization

Variables	X ² calculated	DF	P	Remarks
Age and perception	42.23	24	0.12	S
Marital status and perception	15.15	4	0.004	S
Household size and perception	22.61	8	0.004	S
Level of education and perception	19.65	12	0.014	NS
Sex and perception	5.83	4	0.212	NS
Religion and perception	11.58	4	0.021	S

Although, level of education has been found to be significantly related to level of adoption (Alfred 2004; Alfred, 2006), the technique of door to door approach, the enlightenment through the electronic and print media, including the use of posters and hand bills, might have eroded the necessity of level of education for the people to be mobilized and be involved. Therefore, irrespective of the level of education, the people participated.

CONCLUSION

The assumption has always been that, if children fully take the immunization as specified by EPI, there would be a drastic reduction in the percentage of deformed children and child mortality. This study has found that more of younger mothers participated and generally, there was a high level of participation in EPI. The high level of participation cannot be divorced from the fact that the method of information dissemination was effective and timely as the people confirmed that they were very much aware of the programme. The use of electronic media, with which the people were mostly informed, was responsible for the feat. The provision of the immunization at the non-expense of the target group must be seen as a great motivating factor for the high participation. It is therefore recommended that the zero payment for immunization should continue. Secondly, it cannot be out of place if local town criers are used to inform the communities a day to the programme as there is the possibility of the willing participants forgetting even when they were aware of it few days to the program. Rural people very much appreciate roles of town criers in information dissemination.

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